
Financial Support of Pre-School Educational Institutions Based on Public Private Partnership

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Abstract: This article discusses the potential of public-private partnerships to support preschools based on public-private partnerships, to finance quality preschool education, and to support early childhood education is fully described.

Key words: Public-private partnership, pre-school educational institutions, educational services, financial stability, investments.

Today, the world education system is rapidly developing. As a result, new innovative technologies are widely introduced in this field. In particular, a number of scientific studies dedicated to the in-depth study of preschool education, reconstruction and modernization of the field on the basis of deep structural changes is one of the most important issues of today.

One of the most difficult problems for young families in Uzbekistan is low access to preschool education. Low-income families and families living in villages face difficulties in using educational services. This education is especially important for the development of young children, and "gaps in early childhood development affect later educational attainment and adult productivity."

Although preschool education is not a public service in Uzbekistan, its social goal is to provide equal opportunities for all children in education. If the current situation does not change, it will be difficult for representatives of different nationalities to succeed in higher education. The consequences of the current economic situation in Uzbekistan have led to difficulties in financing the preschool education system. A funding method is needed to maintain and increase current rates of access to educational services.

Financial sustainability is a key issue in ensuring the sustainability of preschools globally. Various efforts have been made by governments to provide funding for early childhood education as an important aspect of the education system. Private preschool educational institutions are expected to demonstrate a high level of efficiency and quality of services provided in order to create a competitive preschool educational institutions.

It is expected that the financial burden on the state budget will be eased with the launch of public-private private business entities for the financing of new preschool educational institutions, since the initial capital investments for the construction of preschool educational institutions will be financed by private investors, and the state will only have to start paying.

In order to study the financial support of preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan through public-private partnership, it is necessary to study the goals of establishing preschool educational institutions on the basis of public-private partnership. This study provides a basis for understanding the reasons behind the implementation of Public Private Partnerships for the financing of preschool institutions and the use of Public Private Partnerships for subsidizing preschool institutions compared to the use of other forms of financing.

The goals of establishing preschool educational institutions on the basis of public-private partnership in Uzbekistan reflect to a certain extent the expected general goals of establishing preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan. These new preschools, established through a public-private partnership initiative, aim to provide a new and additional source of quality preschools in Uzbekistan, with the expectation of increasing access to preschools and the quality of preschools.

In conclusion, it should be said that one of the promising directions of the country's economy and the future of the nation, the destiny of the country lies in the pre-school education system. Taking this into account, all reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan should be focused on the field of preschool education. Then, in the future, the Republic of Uzbekistan will become a country that exports, not an importer of scientific, innovative and high technologies.

Public-private partnerships in preschool education today is one of the most promising directions of organizing forms.

Interregional budget and private investments in their organization it is necessary to take into account the interests of private organizations in the distribution.

It is also worth saying that it is difficult to distinguish different methods of financial support, and Public Private Partnership projects are the most complex and strategic type of financing. This study will focus primarily on the impact of such funding on preschools themselves, and on the quality and accessibility of preschool education. Second, the impact of public provision on inequality. By using this research project, it is hoped that a holistic view of the impact of Public Private Partnership projects can be obtained by getting to know the actual actors and implementers of the policy.

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